

AlSi10Mg additively manufactured anchors for a novel multimaterial hybrid joining for aerospace

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Abstract

The improvement of the economic and the technological performance of **joining technologies** is currently a hot topic in aviation. Although mechanical bonding such as fasteners and rivets are been one of the common techniques to bond metals with fibre reinforced polymers, they add unnecessary weight, require time consuming assemblies and damage to fibres can occur during handling. These challenges underscore the necessity for alternative solutions in joining technology. **MIMOSA**, an EU funded project, proposes a solution to overcome these limitations: a novel process for **multi-material joining of Additively Manufactured AlSi10Mg and CFRP**. The proposed joining technology exploits the mechanical interlocking mechanism between the CFRPs and the 3D metal anchors. A **lattice structure** is introduced to control the thermal expansion between the two parts, by reducing the superficial stress. This combined detail of design and manufacturing process is patented [1, 2], marking a significant milestone in advancing joint technology within the aerospace industry. In this study, **metal anchors produced in AlSi10Mg via Additive Manufacturing** are analyzed, evaluating their mechanical performance and the feasibility of producing novel multi-material joint structures.

AlSi10Mg anchors specimens as produced and integrated to CFRP.

Heat treatments T-t curves.

Conclusive remarks

High density values were achieved on small-to-medium scale parts upon correction and fine-tuning the **printing parameters** for bulk production specimens with AM techniques. From the optimization processes, the parameters that ensure high density for small parts were selected.

	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch spacing [mm]	Layer thickness [mm]	VED [J/mm ³]	LED [J/mm]
Infill	352	1344	0.124	0.03	70.40	-
Contour	304	672	-	-	-	0.45

An **optimization of heat treatments** was also carried out: the goal was to maintain a high density and obtain good mechanical properties. This analysis also took into account the autoclave cure that the AlSi10Mg parts will have to undergo to integrate the CFRP. The highest values of Young modulus and yield stress were achieved with the heat treatment composed by: **Stress relieving (2h at 200°C), Solution Annealing (less than 10min at 530°C), Quenching in water (30s), Artificial Aging (6h at 140°C), Fast air cooling and Autoclave Curing (175min at 175°C).**

The mechanical and physical properties of the optimised parts of AlSi10Mg with a LB-PBF process are the stepping stone for the future of AM joining metal-composite technologies in aeronautical sector.

1. De Pasquale et al.. Composite-metal joint based on engineered surface and related manufacturing method. Patent n. IT812019000097134. 2019.
2. De Pasquale. Wing structure based on conformed metallic elements and relative method of construction. Patent n. IT102020000012619. 2020.